

Aerofracture through a double looking glass, mixing optics and acoustics

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1 Introduction

The characterization and comprehension of rock deformation processes due to fluid flow is a challenging problem with numerous applications in many fields. This phenomenon has received an ever-increasing attention in Earth Science, Physics, with many applications in natural hazard understanding, mitigation or forecast (e.g. earthquakes, landslides with hydrological control, volcanic eruptions), or in the industry, as in CO₂ sequestration, production and reservoir exploitation, or borehole stability problems.

Even though fluid flow, rock deformation [1] or granular dynamics [2] are vast phenomena to understand individually [3], the coupled behaviour of flow in deformable porous media with a dynamic fluid flow makes the system even more intricate to comprehend. The dynamic interaction between flow and the porous media, rapid changes in the local porosity due to the compaction, dilation and migration of the porous material, fracturing due to the momentum exchange in fast flow, make understanding of such a complex system a challenge. [4, 5]

2 State of the Art

There have been several studies carried out recently related to the solid-fluid interactions. Vinningland in 2006 studied the coupling between air and the granular material falling down under the effect of gravity in a Hele-Shaw cell [6, 7, 8]. From 2006 to 2008, Johnsen studied coupled behaviour by injecting air into non-saturated and saturated medium and observed the multiphase flow, decompaction and fluidization in a Hele-Shaw cell [9, 10, 11]. Following these studies, Niebling [12] studied coupling between glycerol/water solution and granular material similar to Vinningland's work. During these works, numerical models have been developed and the results compared successfully with the experiments [9, 12, 13, 14].

In this study, we present an experimental approach to understand coupled behavior by aerofracturing very fine granular medium inside a Hele-Shaw cell. The experiments are monitored using a combination of techniques, both from geophysics and from experimental fluid mechanics to obtain information to understand solid-fluid interaction.

3 Description of the Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consists of a rectangular Hele-Shaw cell with three closed boundaries and one semi-permeable boundary which enables the passage of the fluid but not the solid particles. In the current stage of the research, air is used as the intruding fluid. The Hele-Shaw cell used in the

experiments consist of two rectangular glass plates with a size of 80cm x 40cm which are placed on top of each other. For the initial experiments the structure used is the three boundaries are impermeably sealed and one of the short edges is semi-permeable (i.e. fluid can go out but grains remain inside the cell). The air injection is done from a point which is close to the sealed short edge (2 cm) and on the central line with respect to the longer edges. The Figure 1 [a] shows a Hele-Shaw cell in the mentioned experimental setup.

Figure 1: a) Hele-Shaw Cell used in the experiments. b) Material used in the experiment c) Channeling in the Hele-Shaw Cell

The material used inside the Hele-Shaw cell is made of non-expanded polystyrene (Figure 1 [b]), so-called Ugelstad spheres. The grain size used in the experiments is 80 microns diameter $\pm 1\%$. The density of the grains is $1.005g/cm^3$. Depending on the solid fraction used in the experiment the approximate amount of material used is 150g. For image processing, some of the grains are dyed using the Indian ink. This method increases the contrast between the pixels and help to provide better input data to the image correlation methods.

During the experiments, the fluid is injected into the system from the point opposite to the semi-permeable boundary so that the fluid penetrates into the solid and makes a way via creating channels, fractures or directly using the pore network to the semi-permeable boundary. In the Figure 1 [c] channeling in a horizontal experimental setup due to air injection can be seen.

Experiments are monitored via a high speed camera (up to 1000 fps) and various acoustic sensors which are sensitive to the different frequency ranges. Therefore, in the end it is possible to visualize the solid-fluid interaction by processing images and acoustic emissions. These experimental data can be used to have information about the mechanical properties of the solid partition by analyzing separately and checking the compatibility frequently between the results obtained.

4 Seismic Interpretation

During those interactions between the solid and the fluid phase, microseismic and acoustic signals are emitted which are recorded by various types on sensors - namely Piezoelectric Shock Accelerometer (Freq. range: 1 Hz - 26 kHz) and Piezoelectrical Sensors (Freq. range: 100 kHz - 1 MHz) - placed on the glass plates. To avoid misunderstanding, in the latter parts of this report Piezoelectric Shock Accelerometer will be referred as Accelerometer.

The acoustic sensors are so far primarily used to understand the characteristic elastic properties of the glass plates and the Lamb waves that are propagating in them. As the project continues the acquired signals will be used to have information about the physical interaction between fluid and solid particles. Several controlled signals (using a signal generator, steel ball drop, hammer hit) are

produced to understand the response of the experimental setup and verify the scripts for source localization prior to the air injection experiments. After defining the parameters to characterize the glass plates, the procedure involving the analysis of the acoustic emissions due to fractures started. Recorded signals created by channeling and fracturing are compared and investigated further in both time and frequency domains. Moreover, by using different techniques localization of the acoustic emissions are done, compared and developed. Localizing the source can give vital information about the systems for aero-fracturing for the conditions where the visual data is not available.(e.g. aero-fracturing in a borehole).

4.1 Signal Localization

Here in this project, several methods have been tried out and compared for localization. First, the classical method using the arrival time delay between different sensors is tried out. Arrival times at each sensor are calculated using the numerical modeling in addition to the experimental data. The numerical model is constructed using the experimentally obtained group velocity of the Lamb waves and the model is used to calculate all possible arrival time delays for all possible sources in the medium. The experimentally obtained delay in the arrival time is then compared with those results to find the best fit between the experimental results. Both data is correlated using the least squares error method to find possible points which correspond to the location of the source of the signal received in the receivers.

Localization via signal energy is based on the fact that attenuation of the signal energy in glass plates is homogenous and very low. Therefore the energy recorded every position in the plate should be equal (or at least very close) to each other. Using the fact that the Equation 1 depends on the distance between the source and the receiver, the location can be found with a trial and error procedure. Below in the two flow charts the methods are also explained stepwise. [15] [16]

$$E_s = 2\pi Rh\rho \int V_g \frac{|a_2(\omega)|^2}{\omega^2} \exp(\gamma R) d\omega, \quad (1)$$

where R is the distance between source and the receiver, h is the half-thickness of the plate, $a(\omega)$ is the amplitude in fourier domain, V_g is the group velocity, ω is the angular frequency, γ is the attenuation coefficient which is taken as 0 for glass plates used in this experiment.

To validate the localization methods, several set of experiments are conducted by dropping a steel ball to a fixed location in the glass plates. The results of the two methods were similar to each other and were giving results with a 2cm precision. As it can be seen in the Figure 3 methods are successful to find the location of the signal source.

A limitation of the arrival time based method relies on the following approximation: the localization using the arrival time delay makes the assumption that the group velocity of the Lamb waves is the same everywhere in the glass plates, although it can vary slightly. On the other hand, a limitation of the other method arises from the following: calculating the energy without taking into account reflecting waves from sides of the glass plates is another difficulty.

For comparison, both methods are applied to the signal received during an experiment to locate the event.

Above in the Figure 4 the comparison of the two localization methods on a signal received during the air injection can be seen. It should be noted that both methods give results very close to each other as in the validation phase. It is not easy to conclude that one is better than the other. This would require a comparison of both results with a third technique, as e.g. the localization results obtained from image processing. However, for now it can be said that arrival time delay localization is faster to compute than the localization using the signal energy.

Figure 2: Flowchart explaining two different localization processes.

Figure 3: Validation of the Localization Methods using a Steel Ball. Figures on the left column shows localization result using the arrival time delay. Figures on the right column shows localization result using the signal energy.

Figure 4: Localization of the signal received during an experiment. The figure of the left side shows localization result using the arrival time delay. The figure on the right shows localization result using the signal energy.

5 Investigation of optical data

One advantage of performing experiments in a Hele-Shaw cell is that we can optically see what happens inside it during experiments. The optical part of our experimental data is recorded in the form of image sequences with a very high framerate (1000 frames per second (fps)). These image sequences are captured from a top-down view over the cell and gives us a detailed overview of the experiments ($15\text{px} \approx 1\text{cm}$) with a fine time resolution. Investigation of the optical data involves image processing on a large set of images where the purpose is to characterize and locate flow events both in position and time, extract time-evolving quantities of the pattern formation and investigate granular compaction. The different techniques we can use and the quantities possible to extract will be presented in this section.

5.1 Pattern segmentation

Granular fracturing in our experiments is seen as regions or channels where the initial granular packing has been displaced by air and emptied of grains. The bottom of the cell is black, so that an emptied region is seen as an area of dark pixels. On the other hand, the granular media is white and is seen as an area of brighter grey pixels. Therefore, the granular packing and emptied pattern, as shown in the top-middle image of figure 5, are in principle easy to distinguish with a pixel intensity threshold.

To highlight the empty structure formed during an experiment as a change in the granular packing we make a modified image sequence where all the frames in the raw-data are subtracted pixel by pixel by the image of the initial packing. The resulting difference images display the emptied structure as a bright region and non-displaced parts as a dark region, shown in figure 5. After highlighting the emptied pattern, the images are converted into segmented binary images. This means that the pixels we want to measure in the images are given the pixel value "1" and the rest of the pixels are given the pixel value "0". The emptied pattern is the interesting part in this case, and can be selected as the pixels having a value above a certain threshold intensity. The bottom image in figure 5 shows an example of a binary pattern image.

Measurable time-dependent quantities of the emptied structure include basic spatial characteristics as indicated in figure 6. These quantities are the total width $w(x, t)$ of the structure at the position x and time t , the area $A(t)$ of the pattern at time t , the number of fingers $n(x, t)$ crossed by a perpendicular line at the position x and time t , and the length $l(t)$ of the most advanced finger at time t . Other optically obtained quantities of the pattern that can be investigated over time are the fractal dimension, the splitting characteristics of fingers and the resting times between events in e.g. stick-slip motion.

Figure 5: Image b) shows the intensity difference between the granular packing (grey) and the air-filled region of the cell (black). The top image a) shows the image of the initial packing, and c) shows the emptied pattern (grey) as the difference $a) - b)$. The bottom image d) shows the segmented binary image from c)

Figure 6: Indications of the measurable quantities of the pattern: the total width w , area A , length of the most advanced finger l and the number of fingers n . The "1" pixels are white and the "0" pixels are black. The x -direction is from the closed short-side toward the semi-permeable short side, and the time t is the experimental time of the frame.

5.2 Granular particle tracing

As we have tracer particles in the granular packing, we can perform an image correlation technique called PIV (Particle Image Velocimetry) on the image sequences. This technique will give us the average velocity field of the tracer particles on the time between two subsequent images. Currently we have not yet performed PIV on a frame-to-frame basis in order to investigate quantities, but the idea is that we can use the displacement fields to estimate and locate changes in packing density, track the front between the compacted/uncompacted areas in the solid and investigate particle movements in the solid. We have tested the compability of the image sequences with PIV by trying the software on selected frame pairs, and by the look of the results we can conclude that the software is able to track the particles. Figure 7 shows an example of such a PIV test result.

A quantity we can measure of the compacted region, i.e. the region of the solid where particles have been displaced, is the length of the compaction. This is measured in the x -direction (flow direction) from the emptied pattern to the displacement front, and indicates how deep the fluid-solid interaction penetrates the solid. It is of interest to compare the length of the compaction region with the length of the emptied structure along lines in various parts of the compaction. A similar comparison can be done between the area of the compaction region and the area of the emptied structure. We can also look at the progress of the longest compaction length over time. Another quantity we can try to investigate is the particle density distribution around the emptied structure.

Figure 7: Example of a PIV field between the initial packing and the pattern image in figure 5. Blue represents unmoved particles and red is the highest velocity magnitude in the frame. Because of the relatively large time separation of the selected frames, the velocity field close to the emptied region (white) is poorly defined. However, the banana-shaped part to the right of the velocity field gives a good visualization of the extent of the compaction front.

6 Results

6.1 Signal Analysis in Fourier Domain

The acoustic recordings are also investigated by using several techniques. Below in the figures a horizontal Hele-Shaw cell setup is given. During the experiment 1.5 bar pressurized air is injected into the cell during 6 seconds starting from $t = 1sec$. The changes in frequencies can be seen by cutting pieces in time domain and visualizing them after Fourier transform.

Figure 8 shows the initial situation in the cell. The uppermost plot shows the signal and the red rectangle shows the signal part to be focused in the lower two images. For the plot showing partial signal in Fourier domain after Fourier transformation Hanning window is also applied. Please note that the low frequency amplitude in the Fourier domain is slightly higher. This can be due to the random noise present in the lab environment.

Figure 9 shows the cell and the signal received when the pumping starts. Bulk movement of grains due to air injection creates 4 peaks in the Fourier domain around 1 kHz, 30kHz, 50 kHz and 200 kHz.

When channeling stops the only movement is due to the stress redistribution in the grains which creates the micro events which is similar to tremors. Since there is not a bulk movement the peak in the 1kHz range is getting smaller. However, as long as the injection continues the peak exists. Furthermore, it can be seen that the peaks at 30kHz and 200kHz have disappeared when channeling reaches its final form, and only a steady flow of air remains through the system.

Figure 8: Signal Recordings and Time Windows. The uppermost image shows the Hele-Shaw cell on the instant of the signal received inside the red rectangle. The signal received during the whole experiment is given in the first plot. The instantaneous signal is transferred to the power spectrum which is shown in the lowermost plot.

Figure 9: Signal Received during Air Injection

Figure 10: Signal Received after Channel Formation

7 Conclusion and future plans

So far we have tested the experimental equipment, setup and procedures of aerofracturing in a dry, non-consolidated powder in a rectangular and closed Hele-Shaw cell with a fluid-permeable short edge. By trial and error, we have developed stepwise experimental procedures and sample preparation methods. When we prepare the experimental samples by following the same steps each time, we can create fairly reproducible initial conditions, although the randomness of the particle arrangement will always account for some differences.

For the acoustic emissions, we have investigated the acoustic properties of our experimental equipment and evaluated two methods of signal location of signals emitted by different sources. We have also received and investigated signals emitted by fracturing events during experiments.

When we consider the optical data, we see that the contrast between the granular material and emptied structure is good, and we have successfully converted raw image data into segmented binary images of the emptied structure. From these segmented images we can quickly extract observable quantities of the pattern using a script. The tracer particles dyed with India ink also prove to be sufficiently contrasted to be tracked during PIV, so that we can obtain particle displacement fields between frames of the image sequences.

The conclusion is that we have developed experimental procedures that works and have a setup which enables us to perform reproducible aerofracturing experiments. We are able to obtain a lot of optical and acoustic data to investigate and compare.

We have done the initial work to establish experimental methods, and are now ready to conduct repeated experiments with given initial conditions. This will provide us with several sets of optical and acoustic data, which we can analyze separately and also compare to each other. Specifically, we want to compare acoustic signal localization with optical observations near the located source. We also aim to systematically change initial conditions, such as injection pressure and initial packing density, and investigate the effects on the acoustic signals and observed quantities. We will also use a pressure sensor at the air injection site in order to have a reading on the pressure of the intruding air, which is nearly constant in the air-filled region of the cell.

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